

Identity Transformation and Marginalization: The Process of Sheikization Among Dalji Muslims in Coastal Karnataka

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Abstract

This study aims to explore the process of Islamization or "Sheikization" among the Dalji Muslims. This process involves a shift in identity, as evidenced by the adoption of 'Sheik' surnames and an attempt to distance themselves from the term 'Dalji' due to perceived stigma. The narrative outlines the socio-cultural challenges faced by the Dalji Muslims, who, despite their hardworking nature and dedication to fishing activities, feel marginalized within the broader Muslim society in coastal Karnataka. This marginalization is attributed to their occupational identity and traditional practices, which hinder their integration into the mainstream Muslim community. The study involves an in-depth exploration of the historical, social, and cultural factors contributing to the process of identity transformation among the Dalji Muslims. It may also delve into the implications of this transformation on their access to government benefits, given the shift in self-identification from Dalji to 'Sheik.' The study is likely to contribute valuable insights into the complex dynamics of identity, marginalization, and adaptation within a specific community context. This study is a part of Doctoral research carried out at Karnatak University, Dharwad

Introduction:

India is the World's largest Hindu populated country with the 79.89% of the population while 14.2% of population has identifying as Muslims and remaining 6% of the population belong to the various indigenous religions. Muslims in India are the second largest religious minority community of the country. Being a largest minority community it is facing various Socio- Economic problems. And it has not changed much in free India. In this regard social stratification is one of the major problems among Muslims through which various Muslim groups are facing marginalization which leads them to identity transformation to achieve better status in society.

As Quran and Hadiths (sayings of prophet) are the basic sources of knowledge in Islam, which no Muslim can ever deny. Although Muslims give primary importance to Quran. If we go through Quranic verses, we can see that, Islam is totally opposed to all forms

of social stratification. For the purpose of illustration one of the Quranic verses says, “O mankind We (God) created you from a single pair of male and female; and make you into peoples and tribes with each other (not that ye may despise each other). Verily the most honoured in the sight of God is (he who is) the most righteous among you.....” (The Quran 49:13). This verse clear that Islam does not allow any social stratification but only it admit the social differentiation on the basis of Gender and racial affiliation. As Siddqui (1974) points out, “The story of creation given currency through Quranic verse envisages the propagation of mankind out of a single couple Adam and Eve and the dispersal of human species on earth from a single centre. Fitting well into the texture of Islamic belief which regard to human society, the theories of human origin and dispersal render all claims to superiority, not only based on race and colour but also on region and language, as irrelevant and unacceptable”.

Though Muslims in India follow monolithic religion, they are sharply divided on the basis of their language, beliefs and practices. Universally they are follow four schools of Islamic thought. They are Hanafi, Malaki, Shafi and Hambali. In India, we come across the followers of all these schools of thought. However most of them follow Hanafi School. However, there is neither a difference between upper and lower, pure and impure nor racial, and there is no categorization in Islam on the name of caste. Scholars like Blunt (1969), Ansari (1960), Imtiaz Ahmad (1966), and Zarina Ahmad (1962) found the stratification among Muslims which is mostly found in India. According to Mondal (2003) “The differentiation that emerged among the Muslims at first is between the descendants of the so-called 'foreign ancestors' and the indigenous converts. The former segment is known as Ashraf or khas, while the latter segment is called as Ajlaf or atraf or aam. Those who called themselves ashraf are the gentry and considered themselves as aristocrats. They are the landowners, Civic and Religious Leaders and comparatively wealthier”. It is fact that the categorization of Ashrafs and Ajlafs which also determine the status based on occupation is become the main reason of differentiate people within their own community.

Imtiaz Ahmad questions the relevance of the Ashraf and Ajlaf distinction in society. He observes that a complete understanding of social stratification among Muslims in India necessitates an exploration of the interrelations between the Ashraf and Ajlaf groupings. He concludes that the "Ashraf-Ajlaf dichotomy has produced an oversimplified picture of the nature of social stratification among Muslims. It is, in fact, a complex hierarchical system composed of a large number of social units, which are small, named groups of individuals characterized by endogamy, hereditary membership, and a distinct style of life." These

Ashrafs and Ajlafs are further divided into several smaller groups. For example, the Ashrafs are subdivided into four major sub-groups: Saiyed, Shaikh, Moghal, and Pathan. Similarly, the Ajlafs are divided into various small local groups.

This complexity within the Muslim community has led to the formation of caste-like groups, causing some Muslim groups to lose their distinct identity and become marginalized within the broader Muslim society. Against this background, the present study focuses on the Dalji Muslims, a marginalized Muslim fishing community found along the western coast of Karnataka. This study analyzes the process of Sheikhization among the Dalji Muslims, a shift in identity involving the abandonment of their original surnames and the adoption of the title "Sheikh." Belonging to the "impure" occupation of fishing has been a significant factor contributing to their marginalization and perceived inferiority in socio-economic fields. The study also examines the historical, social, and cultural factors influencing the identity transformation of the Dalji Muslims.

Social Stratification among Muslims:

Generally it is believed that the Religion of Islam is egalitarian and does not advocate caste or any other type of Stratification. Ahmed and Chakravarti (1981:56) states that "According to Islam, Every Muslim is born equal in the eyes of God and a Muslim can find no refuge in religion to justify the practice of social inequality". Scholars often cite Prophet Mohammed's farewell Khutba where he had famously said, "There is no superiority of an Arab over a non- Arab, or of a non-Arab over an Arab, and no superiority of a White person over a Black person or of a black person over a White person, except on the basis of personal piety and righteousness" (Pratik Patnaik 2020).

Hence, Islam provides equality among Muslims and there is no inequality, stratification and hierarchy proved by Quran and Shariah .Stratification among Muslim groups comes through the social position and not by religion. One of the great pioneers of caste and Stratification Among Muslim, Ghaus Ansari (1960) give three categories of Muslim caste which is known as Ashrafs, Ajhlafs and Arzals commonly it is known as upper caste and lower caste and the brief meaning of 'Ashraf' are the pure and foreign descendents and upper class Hindus (Rajputs) converted to Islam, where as Ajhlafs are clean occupational castes and Arzals are unclean or Untouchables. Here we come across the Karl marx's theory of stratification where he says that "there were two main classes of social stratification which is Proletariate (workers) and Buorgeiosie (owners of the means of production)". This

classification indicates the Socio Economic status of individuals in society. Many Scholars broadly acknowledge the Hindu Varna system but the famous sociologists like Louis Dumont (1980), T.N.Madan (1972) did not observe any caste system among Muslims due to the perceived absence of the over arching ideological principle guiding the structure. It is clear that the categorization among Muslim is not religious but because of social position. Anyhow stratification among Muslim is present and almost same like Varna system where Brahmins are on the top like Ashrafs who are Sayed, Shaikh, Mughal or Pathan (owners) and Ajlaf are like vaishyas who are categorise by their clean occupation like small businesses, Darzi (tailor), Qasai (meat seller), manihar (bangle seller) etc. While there is one more category called Arzal the unclean and impure caste who are sweepers and scavengers like Pancham Varna or Untouchables.

Ashrafization Among Muslims:

When caste hierarchy is based on purity and impurity then every caste trying to change their rank by giving up their own attributes and trying to adopt or imitate the characteristics of upper caste. For this process M.N.Srinivas called 'Sanskritization'(1962). Though here we can see the same process in Muslims which is 'Ashrafization' the term coined by Cora Vreede-de Sluvers (1968) to describe the 'Attempts at social climbing by groups or individual through hypergamy and adopting the way of life of higher classes' (Levesque and Niazi,2023).

In Islam the process of Ashrafization took place when lower Muslims or Ajhlafs start to imitate the culture as well as structure of Ashrafs, like dressing style, food habitation. Islamic traditions etc, along with this they are giving up many attributes in social field like small marriages in Mosques to grand marriages in hall with decoration. Though this process shows not only adoption of culture and nature of the upper caste but also adopt their surnames. The most significant case occurred among Julahas (Weavers) of Peshawar, they adopted the title of Ansari, signifying the companions of the Prophet (Pandey. 1983) and established a Momin conference in 1924 in Culcutta (Ghosh, 2020), In 1927, another important organization emerged in Delhi to represent butchers, meat, hide and leather traders under the banner of the All India Jamiat-ul Quraish (Z.Ahmad 2018a Niazi 2020a). Similarly, several smaller associations were formed to mobilize other *peshewar birādarīs*, including the Mirasis (musicians and genealogists) and the Arains (vegetable sellers and gardeners

[Koul 2017]. All these associations linked their respective *biradaris* to the Sheikh status. As this study is focuses on the process of identity shifting among Dalji Muslims who are one of the marginalised Muslim group. This community make an attempt to adopt the process of Ashrafization in order to shifting their identity from lower status to higher status in society. During this process they also given up their original surnames and adopt the title of Sheikh. Keeping this same thing in mind, Tausif Ahmad (2023) suggests the term ‘Shaikhization’ instead of Ashrafization.

Social Groups among Muslims in India

Within the Indian Muslim society, we find different social groups. They are Shaikh, Sayyad, Mughal and Pathan. This is basically similar groups with distinct names. Though exact history of these groups does not exist, all are following Islamic principles and tenets. Shaikhs are generally denotes often refers to a respected leader or elder in Arab societies. In India most of the Muslims have retained their surnames as Shaikh. Sayyads claim their descent from the Prophet Muhammad through his daughter. Therefore they hold a high social status due to their lineage of Prophet Mohammad. Mughals in India are historically the rulers of Indian sub continent. Pathans are tribals groups originated from Afghanistan-Pakistan border regions. Most of them served as soldiers and administrators .

Who Are Sheikh?

To know who is Sheikh we should go through the History of Islam from where the actual categorization or classification begin among Muslims. As Islam is the Monotheistic religion, meaning that its followers believe in one Supreme God Allah. And the Prophet Muhammad is the last Prophet of Ummah (the whole community of Muslims bound together by ties of religion) from Him. Allah Ta’ala revealed the Holy Quran to his Prophet which equips man with Islamic education and along with Hadiths (sayings of Prophet) and Shariah (Islamic Law) shows Muslims the right way to live a life according to the Islamic way. However, in Islam every human being is equal in the eye of God and Prophet. As Holy Quran declares, *O mankind Lo. We have created you male and female and made you nations and tribes, that you may know one another,(Al-Quraan 49:13). “All people are single nation (2:213) and people are naught but a single nation” (10:19)*. These are the mesaages of Holy Quraan.

Until the lifetime of the Prophet Mohammad there was no leader in Islam except Him. After the Prophet Mohammad died, there was a disagreement start over who should succeed

him. As a result two groups emerged for the first time in Islam; one is Sunnis, who believed that four religious leaders known as the Caliphs should be the new leaders, They are; Hazrath Umar Farooq, Hazrath Usman Gani, Hazrat Abu Bakr Siddique and Hazrat Ali, and the second group is 'Shiah' who believed that only one of the Khalif Hazrat Ali, and his bloodline should follow the leadership. However the majority of Muslims are Sunnis while only one part of Muslims in the World are known as Shiah Muslims. Universally Sunni Muslims are following four school of Islamic thought. The four prominent school of Islamic Law are named after their founders and are called, The Hanafi, The Shafi, The Maliki and The Hanbali.

In this backdrop, now we should move to the question who are Sheikh? It is observed that the word 'Sheikh' is one of the surnames of those groups who are belonging to Category of 'Ashrafs'. The word "Sheikh" is an Arabic term which means 'Elder'. According to oxford dictionary of world religion (2023) Sheikh means Old man, Chief, or elder, a title of respect in Islam, especially for religious leader. As Sheikh is an Arabic word, it came to India when Arabs came here as traders more than thousand years ago. They are the true descendents of Prophet Muhammad and they were married to the local women of the country to continue their lineage and they are known as Sheikh, Saiyed, etc. Sheikhs are always known for trade and business. The title of Sheikh is provide adequate respect like Ashrafs. According to Levesque (2023) "The Sheikh status offered sufficient fluidity for various Muslim occupational castes, or 'biradaris' to adopt Arab surnames". As the word Sheikh is Arab origin who are following the Shafi School of Thought. But most of the Hanfi Muslims also using the surname as Sheikh. But it is noticed that, large numbers of Sheikhs are found in Northern part of India, who are generally explained as resulting from social mobility among Muslims. As Mandelbaum (1970) notes a common sayings that, "We used to be butchers and now we are Sheikhs. Next year if the harvest prices are good for us, we shall be Sayyeds". It indicates that social mobility among Muslims can be very rapidly increase.

Who Are Dalji Muslims?

The Dalji is one of the marginalized Muslim communities located along the southern coast of India. The people of this community are known as Daldi, Dalji, or Nakhuda, as their primary occupation is fishing. This community is primarily found in the coastal region extending from Shiroor village in Udupi District to Bhatkal, Honnavar, Kumta, Ankola, and Karwar, the last city of Karnataka bordering Goa. The total population of the Dalji

community is approximately 15,000, with Shiroor village alone accounting for around 5,000 people. In addition to Karnataka, members of this community are also found in Ratnagiri city and the Bhandi Bazaar area of Mumbai in Maharashtra. However, due to a lack of strong mutual ties between these regions, the social status of this community has remained weak. The Dalji community is also known for its unique language, *Daldi*, which is a dialect of Konkani or Goan Konkani. While Goan Konkani exhibits Portuguese influences and, to a lesser extent, Marathi, Muslim Konkani dialects like Nawayathi and Siddi reflect Persian and Arabic influences. Similarly, the Daldi language shows influences from the Nawayathi dialect, incorporating Arabic, Persian, Konkani, and Marathi elements. Except for the Dalji Muslims of Karwar, most of the community members still use the Daldi language. However, it has been observed that this community is gradually moving away from their mother tongue, with the younger generation increasingly adopting Dakni Urdu.

According to Nadvi Ibrahim (2018), the Dalji community was historically involved in sailing and shipbuilding. They engaged in trade and transported various goods between ports using their cargo sailing ships. The primary items transported included food products, spices, different types of timber, coconut oil, kerosene, and dried fish. Their merchant ships plied routes from Gujarat to Kanyakumari. Members of this community also crafted cords and ropes from coconut shells to support their profession and were skilled in building large commercial cargo ships, which they referred to in their language as *Machwa*, while smaller ships were called *Bark*. Additionally, they constructed special ships for foreign voyages, designed to navigate against opposing winds, which they called *Tar*. They were also adept at finding directions using the stars. This profession persisted until the late 14th century. However, with advancements in commercial transportation and the advent of machine boats, the Daljis transitioned to fishing as their primary occupation in the early 15th century. Fishing remains the main livelihood of the community to this day.

Due to poverty, members of the Dalji community are often engaged in fishing day and night, leaving them disconnected from broader social and political activities. This has contributed to their backwardness in social, political, and economic spheres compared to other Muslim groups in the region. The community has been referred to by various names, such as Nakhuda, Dalji, Dawat, Daldi, and Nakhwaji. However, at present, they prefer to be identified as Nakhuda Muslims, as they find the terms "Dalji" or "Daldi" demeaning. The discomfort with these terms stems from their meanings. According to Nadvi Ibrahim (2018), "Dalji" originates from the Arabic word meaning "to draw water from a well and pour

it into a pool." Derived from the active participle *Dalji*, it became *Dalji* with the addition of *Ya Nasbati* in Arabic grammar, which refers to the task of pouring out water from a ship's interior. Historically, the Daljis performed this task when water entered their fishing boats. However, with modern fishing boats becoming mechanized, this meaning now implies a lower occupational status, leading to the community's reluctance to use the term.

Despite their reliance on fishing, this community faces significant economic challenges, especially during the rainy season, when there is no steady source of income. Women often contribute by making fishing nets or selling dried fish. In government records, their caste name is listed as "Dalji." The Nakhuda Association attempted to change this designation to "Nakhuda" in the Karnataka Backward Class Commission's list, but their application was rejected due to a lack of sufficient historical evidence. As a result, they remain classified as "Dalji" under Category 1 in the Karnataka Backward Class Commission's records.

Sheikhization Among Dalji Muslims

It has been observed that almost all Dalji Muslims of coastal Karnataka are adopting the culture of dominant groups, portraying themselves as a dominant caste, and denying their historically marginalized status. Until about four or five years ago, this community was characterized by high levels of illiteracy, minimal participation in politics, and poor economic conditions. Consequently, historical material on this community is scarce. The main reason for their marginalization lies in their historical association with what were considered "impure" occupations, primarily fishing. This is similar to the Mogaveeras, a non-Muslim fishing community of Tulu Nadu in the coastal regions of Karnataka. However, unlike the Dalji Muslims, the Mogaveeras have emerged as one of the dominant maritime communities in the region, despite also being listed as an Other Backward Class (OBC).

In the early 15th century, the Daljis began educating their younger generation, though primarily males, in religious fields such as becoming *Hafiz*, *Alim*, *Qazi*, and *Fazil*. Over time, they gradually moved toward higher education, though women were still denied access to education. In recent years, the Dalji Muslims have become heavily influenced by the Navayat community of Bhatkal. This influence is evident in their adoption of traditional Navayat customs, such as men wearing white *kurta* and *lungi*, while women strictly follow the *purdah* system and wear *burqas* in public. They emphasize religious education over formal schooling, avoid co-education for girls, perform *namaz* five times a day, and regularly attend mosques.

A notable trend among the Dalji Muslims is the shift from Ashrafization to Sheikhization, with many families adopting the title of "Sheikh" as a surname to avoid marginalization. Historically, Dalji Muslims were classified as *Ajlafs* (backward Muslims) and were often subjected to social humiliation by dominant Muslim groups. To escape this stigma, many families changed their surnames to "Sheikh." Traditional Dalji surnames such as Zingru, Shamali, Langdo, Sanukar, Dangi, Honnekar, Hamaji (Ahmedji), Khoja (associated with a Muslim group in Mumbai), Ingreji, and Khatlo have been replaced by surnames like Umar, Unchali, Hukka, and Battikar.

The motivation behind adopting "Sheikh" as a surname lies in its association with Arab descent and its prestige within the Shafi'i school of Islamic thought, which the Dalji Muslims follow. This practice aligns with broader patterns observed among other Muslim occupational castes. As Levesque (2023) notes, "Among Muslim occupational castes, adopting a Sheikh status is often part of upward social mobility." Similar trends are seen in communities like the Julahas (weavers) of Peshawar, who adopt the title "Ansari" (signifying the companions of the Prophet), and butchers and leather traders from Delhi, who also change their surnames to "Sheikh" (Z. Ahmad, 2018; Niazi, 2020; Pandey, 1983).

Despite these efforts at upward mobility, many Dalji Muslims remain unaware of their official classification under the Karnataka OBC list. According to the Indian Constitution, the Karnataka government provides a 4% reservation for Category-I castes, but members of the Dalji community often mistakenly identify themselves as belonging to Category II-B, which is creamy layer category. Community members argue that a lack of awareness about these reservations and entitlements has hindered their access to education for their children. Instead of embracing their communal identity as Daljis, they seek to rebrand their community as "Nakhuda," meaning "master of the boat," and distance themselves from their traditional surnames by adopting the prestigious title of "Sheikh."

Interestingly, the Dalji Muslims of Karwar are an exception. Although they also follow the Shafi'i school of thought, they are no longer dependent on fishing as an occupation. Most families in this subgroup have already adopted the surnames "Sheikh" and "Khan," reflecting a more successful integration into dominant cultural norms.

Conclusion

The present study is based on secondary data and is part of a doctoral research project conducted at Karnatak University, Dharwad. It highlights the backwardness of the Dalji Muslim community and aims to introduce this fishing Muslim group, whose existence is scarcely known even to some neighboring Muslim and non-Muslim communities. The study explores the processes of Ashrafization and Sheikhization among the Dalji Muslims and reveals how their association with what is considered an "unclean" occupation, categorized under the Ajlaf, has contributed to their marginalization. To avoid this marginalization, members of the Dalji community have increasingly adopted the surname "Sheikh" and embraced elements of Ashrafization and Islamization to elevate their status in society. However, to address the root causes of their marginalization, the community needs to engage fully in social and political activities to improve their visibility and representation. They must prioritize providing comprehensive education to the younger generation rather than focusing solely on changing their community name or adopting new surnames. Furthermore, it is essential for the Dalji Muslims to become aware of and leverage the benefits and reservations available to them under their designated category in the Karnataka OBC list. By focusing on these areas, the community can work toward achieving genuine social and economic upliftment.

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